

HeH₂⁺ : A Case Study in *ab initio* Dynamics†

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We review some of our classical mechanical and quantum mechanical investigations of the reaction, He+H₂⁺→HeH⁺+H and its isotopic analog He+HD⁺→HeH⁺+D, HeD⁺+H as well as the dissociative channel He+H₂⁺→He+H+H⁺ over a wide range of translational energies for different vibrational states of H₂⁺(HD⁺) while at the same time relating them to experimental and theoretical studies from other laboratories.

THE HeH₂⁺ system has been the focus of attention of several experimental and theoretical studies for the last two decades. In view of the reaction,

being endothermic ($\Delta E_0^0 = 0.8$ eV) and of the ion-molecule type, its dynamics is expected to be *and* is different from that of the well-studied and well-understood (H, H₂) system and its isotopic analogs. It is also better suited to state-to-state experimental studies¹ and, indeed, was the first one for which vibrational enhancement was demonstrated experimentally². Being a three-electron system (isoelectronic with H₃), it was amenable to extensive *ab initio* calculations at the configuration-interaction level and as a result the potential-energy surface (PES) for the system has been known to a high level of accuracy (± 1 kcal mol⁻¹) for sometime now³. Since there are no low-lying excited states of HeH₂⁺ (except for the degeneracy that arises in the dissociation channel⁴), charge transfer channel,

is not open at energies of the order of a few eV but the dissociation channel,

is very much open at energies greater than 2.78 eV. As a matter of fact, the collision-induced-dissociation (CID) becomes dominant at higher energies. We review here the experimental results that have been obtained so far on the HeH₂⁺ system (in the energy range 0–10 eV) and also the theoretical studies that have been carried out with special emphasis on results from our own laboratory.

Experimental results

Based on their classic photoionisation experiments, Chupka and coworkers⁵ showed that the excitation function, that is, the dependence of the reaction cross section (σ^E) on the relative translational energy (E_{trans}) of the reactants, exhibited a sharp maximum followed by a rapid decay for the

different vibrational states (v) of H₂⁺. It was clear that there was substantial vibrational enhancement over a wide range of E_{trans} . The dynamical threshold ($E_{\text{th}}^{\text{dy}}$) coincided with the energetic threshold (E_{th}^{e}) for dissociation and at higher energies, dissociation dominated over exchange. The dissociation cross section (σ^D) also showed vibrational enhancement over a range of E_{trans} .

Both reactions (1) and (3) have since been studied by different experimental techniques^{5–7}. We must particularly mention the electron impact ionisation studies^{5a–8} which determined the product energy and angular distributions as well. van Pijkeren *et al.*^{6a,b} reported σ^E values obtained by photoionisation under thermal conditions for $v=0–8$, in agreement with the results of Chupka *et al.* At about the same time, Turner *et al.*^{6c} reported σ^E values obtained by photoionisation under beam conditions for $v=0–4$ over $E_{\text{trans}}=1–8$ eV for reaction (1) as well as its isotopic analog,

Their results differed by a factor of 2 from those of Chupka at low energies for reaction (1). Some more experiments⁷ have been carried out in recent years indicating the continued interest in the dynamics of the system. In the most recent experimental study of the (He, H₂⁺) collisions, Govers and Guyon^{9b} used the threshold-photo-electron-photo-ion-coincidence (TPEPICO) technique to measure σ^E as well as σ^D for $v=0–6$ of H₂⁺ at $E_{\text{trans}}=3.1 \pm 0.7$ eV which were in accord with the earlier findings of Chupka *et al.* In addition, they found the branching ratio ($I^E = \sigma^D/\sigma^E$) to be approximately constant at 0.3 for $v \leq 3$ rising subsequently through 1.6 for $v=4–6$. They inferred from large-angle scattering for both channel products for $v < 3$ that hard type collisions were involved. By a clever analysis⁴ of the H⁺ velocity distribution they also concluded that the CID process from $v=0$ and 1 involved a transition to the first excited PES.

† Rev. Fr. L. M. Yeddanapalli Memorial Award Lecture (1989), delivered under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society on 26 December, 1990 at Bodh Gaya.

Theoretical studies

Quasiclassical trajectory results:

Reaction (1) had been the focus of attention of several structural and dynamical studies. Much of the work done till 1986 had been reviewed in our earlier paper⁸ wherein we had reported the details of our analytic fit of the *ab initio* PES and also results of extensive three-dimensional(3D) quasiclassical trajectory (QCT) calculations. As the reactants He and H_2^+ approach each other, there is a potential well which has the largest depth (~ 0.25 eV) for the collinear geometry and the barrier height for the reaction is the same as its endothermicity (see Fig. 1 for a perspective view of the PES for the collinear geometry). There is no saddle point on the PES but

Fig. 1. Perspective view of the potential-energy surface for collinear $[He-H-H]^+$.

for all practical purposes it can be considered to be the way out in the exit channel. Therefore, the famous Polanyi rules⁹ would suggest substantial vibrational enhancement for the reaction. Indeed this was observed experimentally (vide *supra*) and our 3D QCT calculations reiterated the same. σ^E increased rapidly with increase in ν at low E_{trans} . For $\nu=3$ and above the reaction occurred readily even when E_{trans} was negligibly small. For a given ν , σ^E increased with increase in E_{trans} , reached a maximum and then decreased rapidly before levelling off at higher energies. Although all of the above findings were in excellent accord with the experimental results, there were some quantitative discrepancies between our QCT results and the experimental results, particularly those of Turner *et al.*^{6c}.

We had also reported product angular and product translational energy distributions (PAD and PTED respectively) for different (ν, E_{trans}) and shown that the product molecules were scattered predominantly in the forward direction for $\nu > 0$. For $\nu=0$, at $E_{trans}=3.58$ eV for example, the product molecules were scattered exclusively in the backward hemisphere in agreement with the results from the electron impact ionisation studies^{5a-r}. Although the QCT-computed PTED was in broad agreement with the experiment, the former peaked at about 1.5 eV in contrast to the latter peaking at ~ 2 eV.

Part of the discrepancy between our QCT results and experiments could arise from the inadequacy of the *ab initio* PES and/or its analytic fit and/or the classical approach. McLaughlin and Thompson³ estimated that they had included about 90% of the correlation energy in their potential energy calculations. Our earlier studies¹⁰ for the collinear conformation had shown that much of the dynamics remained unaffected when the correlation energy was not included in the *ab initio* PES. The analytic fit⁸ has about the same accuracy as that of the reported PES values. Although QCT dynamics has been shown to be sensitive to changes in the PES for collinear geometries¹¹, the above factors are not likely to be responsible for the observed discrepancies in the 3D-dynamics. Many of the trajectories for the He- H_2^+ collision ended up with the HeH⁺ having a vibrational energy less than the quantum mechanically allowed zero point energy. The σ^E values computed by neglecting such trajectories showing an 'adiabatic leak' got closer to the results of Lee and coworkers suggesting that quantal effects might be important for the system. It is also possible that there were some problems with the experimental results which were invariably over a distribution of E_{trans} . In addition, it is not clear as to what the rotational state (J) distributions were for the different initial (ν, E_{trans}) conditions. Although preliminary QCT investigations suggested that σ^E values for $J=0$ and 2 (for $\nu=1$ and 2) were not distinguishable from each other, within the statistical error estimates, σ^E could be sensitive to other choices of J , particularly for the higher values of ν .

Turner *et al.* found that $\sigma^E(HeH^+)$ dropped more sharply with E_{trans} than $\sigma^E(HeD^+)$ and that the reaction was strongly vibrationally enhanced at $E_{trans}=1-2$ eV for both the channels (4a) and (4b). At 4 eV, only HeH⁺ formation was slightly vibrationally enhanced and at 8 eV, the HeD⁺ channel showed vibrational inhibition. Our QCT studies¹² showed that for $\nu=2$ and 3, $\sigma^E(HeH^+)$ did drop more sharply with E_{trans} than $\sigma^E(HeD^+)$. For $\nu=0$ and 1, however, the excitation function behaved differently for the two channels. The reaction was strongly vibrationally enhanced at 1-2 eV for both the channels. At 3 eV, HeD⁺ began to show vibrational inhibition. There was serious discrepancy between theory and experiment as regards $\Gamma = \sigma^E(HeH^+)/\sigma^E(HeD^+)$. For example, Γ obtained

from QCT calculations was only half that reported from experiments for HD⁺ ($\nu=4$) at 1 eV at which Γ_{expt} is perhaps the most reliable as the σ^E values are the largest at that energy for both the channels. Although Γ_{expt} exhibited a minimum as a function of E_{trans} around 2–4 eV as predicted by theory, it increased as a function of ν at 1 eV in contrast to the nearly constant value of Γ_{act} .

Interestingly, our QCT results¹² were in keeping with what had been found in general about isotopic branching in reactions of the type,

with preference for a collinear approach. Mayne¹³ concluded recently that XD dominates over XH regardless of the exo/endothemicity of the PES. The dominance of the D-isotopomer over the H can be understood in terms of the light H atom being ejected when the former is formed which is kinematically preferred over the ejection of the heavier D. For a collinear geometry, the results could be interpreted¹⁴ in terms of the potential energy contours in scaled and skewed coordinates¹⁵. The skewing angle is significantly larger for the X–HD approach than for the X–DH. In addition, the exit channel gets wider and the entry channel narrower for the latter while the converse is true for the former implying that the fraction of the reactant vibrational phase leading to products and hence the probability of forming XD is larger than that for XH. Although the HeH₂⁺ (HeHD⁺) dynamics is not dominated by the collinear configuration, it can be considered as representative.

The branching ratio has been known to be sensitive to J . It is possible that the discrepancy between theory and experiment for (He, HD⁺) arises due (in addition to the zero-point-energy effects discussed above) to the non-inclusion of the contributions from nonzero J states of HD⁺. Effect of J on Γ for He, HD⁺ collisions is presently under investigation¹⁶.

We had also investigated¹⁷ the effect of ν and E_{trans} on the dissociation channel vis-a-vis exchange. The experimentally observed vibrational enhancement of CID was nearly quantitatively reproduced by our 3D–QCT calculations which also predicted fairly accurately the E_{trans} dependence of σ^D for $\nu=0$ and 3. Our QCT results suggested an interesting hump in σ^D (E_{trans}) for $\nu=5$ and this remains to be verified experimentally. The competition between the exchange and the dissociation processes as reflected in the branching ratio and its dependence on ν was also satisfactorily predicted by theory. Detailed analysis of individual trajectories revealed that the collinear geometry was not conducive to CID and that for low ν , head-on collisions were important. For the higher ν states, while the low b collisions were important at low and high E_{trans} , grazing collisions became effective at moderate energies.

Quantal results :

The first quantum mechanical calculation¹⁸ on the collinear He–H₂⁺ collisions drew a lot of attention because there was an unusually large number of scattering resonances and the vibrational enhancement seen in experimental results was absent. The resonances were identified¹⁹ as belonging to the compound (Feschbach) category and attributed to the presence of a potential well on the PES while the lack of vibrational enhancement was attributed²⁰ to the constraint of collinear geometry and/or inadequacy of the PES. Our R-matrix calculations²¹ on the *ab initio* PES confirmed that the collinear (He, H₂⁺) collisions were rich in scattering resonances and we were able to assign them to the bound states of the vibrational adiabatic potentials in hyperspherical coordinates²². Recently, Kress *et al.*²³ and Zhang *et al.*²⁴ showed that the reactive scattering resonances are present in 3D-collisions for zero total angular momentum but whether they would survive averaging over the orbital angular momentum for the reactants remains to be checked. Our preliminary investigations²⁵ have shown that they might not. However, highly resolved scattering in the backward direction, in the center-of-mass frame, may reveal the existence of the reactive scattering resonances and hence may enable probing the transition state for the system.

Chaos and fractals in collinear collisions :

The existence of narrow resonances in the (He, H₂⁺) collisions suggests the formation of long-lived complexes. The presence of a potential well and the scaling and skewing arising out of the mass combination of the collision partners would definitely contribute to the lifetime of the collision complex. ‘Action-angle’ plots for the collinear collisions contain *smooth* as well as *chattering* regions, the latter being characteristic of trajectories involving ‘multiple encounters’. A detailed examination reveals the behaviour of the trajectories in the chattering region to be ‘chaotic’ but not stochastic; that is, the trajectories do not ‘fill’ the phase space completely. Increased resolution along the initial vibrational phase axis reveals additional structures: a self-similar pattern repeating itself endlessly with a fractal dimension of 1.94 at $E_{\text{trans}}=0.5$ eV for $\nu=0$ of H₂⁺. The fraction of complex formation, defined as the ratio of the number of trajectories in the chattering region to the total, decreases with increase in energy implying that the trajectories become less and less chaotic. At higher energies, as long as the reaction probability is nonzero and less than unity, the switchover region between non-reactive and reactive bands is characterised by a fractal zone. A more detailed account of these studies is given elsewhere²⁵.

Conclusion

We have tried to summarise the present state of understanding of the dynamics in He+H₂⁺ collisions

from theoretical as well as experimental points of view. It is worth adding that the system continues to draw attention because of the richness of its dynamics.

Acknowledgement

It is the pleasant duty of the author to acknowledge the fact that much of the work described above has been possible only due to the financial support received from the Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi, the INDO-US Sub-commission on Science and Technology, the Indian National Science Academy, New Delhi, and the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi.

References

1. R. D. LEVINE and R. B. BERNSTEIN, "Molecular Reaction Dynamics and Chemical Reactivity", Oxford University Press, New York, 1987.
2. W. A. CHUPKA and M. E. RUSSELL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **49**, 5426; W. A. CHUPKA, J. BERKOWITZ and M. E. RUSSELL, 'Sixth International Conference on the Physics of Electronic and Atomic Collisions', MIT Press, Cambridge, 1969, p. 71; W. A. CHUPKA in "Ion-Molecule Reactions", ed. J. L. FRANKLIN, Plenum, New York, 1972, Vol. 1, p. 72.
3. D. R. McLAUGHLIN and D. L. THOMPSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1979, **70**, 2748.
4. E. A. GISLASON and P.-M. GUYON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1987, **86**, 677; M. SIZUN, G. PARLANT and E. A. GISLASON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1988, **88**, 4294.
5. (a) J. A. RUTHERFORD and D. A. VROOM, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1973, **58**, 4076; (b) R. H. NEYNABER and G. D. MAGNUSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1973, **59**, 825; (c) J. J. LEVENTHAL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1971, **54**, 3279; 1973, **58**, 4710; (d) F. SCHNEIDER, U. HAVEMANN and I. ZÜLICHE, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **256**, 773; (e) F. SCHNEIDER, U. HAVEMANN, L. ZÜLICHE, V. PACAK, K. BIRKINSHAW and Z. HERMAN, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1976, **37**, 323; (f) V. PACAK, U. HAVEMANN, Z. HERMAN, F. SCHNEIDER and L. ZÜLICHE, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1977, **49**, 273; (g) U. HAVEMANN, V. PACAK, Z. HERMAN, F. SCHNEIDER, CH. ZUHRT and L. ZÜLICHE, *Chem. Phys.*, 1978, **28**, 147.
6. (a) D. VAN PIJKEREN, J. VAN ECK and A. NIEHAUS, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1983, **96**, 20; (b) D. VAN PIJKEREN, E. BOLTJES, J. VAN ECK and A. NIEHAUS, *Chem. Phys.*, 1984, **91**, 293; (c) T. TURNER, O. DUTUIT and Y. T. LEE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1984, **81**, 3475.
7. M. BAER, S. SUZUKI, K. TANAKA, I. KOYANO, H. NAKAMURA, Z. HERMAN and D. J. KOURI, *Phys. Rev.*, 1986, **A34**, 1748; T. R. GOVERS and P.-M. GUYON, *Chem. Phys.*, 1987, **113**, 425; M. SCHWEIZER, M. A. ACHTENHAGEN and D. GERLICH, unpublished.
8. T. JOSEPH and N. SATHYAMURTHY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1987, **86**, 704.
9. J. C. POLANYI, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1972, **5**, 161.
10. N. SATHYAMURTHY, *Chem. Phys.*, 1981, **62**, 1.
11. N. SATHYAMURTHY, J. W. DUFF, C. L. STROUD and L. M. RAFF, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1977, **67**, 3563.
12. K. C. BHALLA and N. SATHYAMURTHY, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1989, **160**, 437.
13. H. R. MAYNE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1988, **92**, 6289.
14. D. S. PERRY and J. C. POLANYI, *Chem. Phys.*, 1976, **12**, 37.
15. S. GLASSTONE, K. J. LAIDLER and H. EYRING, "The Theory of Rate Processes", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1947.
16. K. C. BHALLA and N. SATHYAMURTHY, unpublished.
17. S. KUMAR and N. SATHYAMURTHY, *Chem. Phys.*, 1989, **137**, 25.
18. D. J. KOURI and M. BAER, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1974, **24**, 37.
19. F. M. CHAPMAN, JR. and E. F. HAYES, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, **62**, 4400; 1976, **65**, 1032.
20. P. J. KUNTZ and W. N. WHITTON, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1975, **34**, 340; W. N. WHITTON and P. J. KUNTZ, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1976, **64**, 3624.
21. T. JOSEPH and N. SATHYAMURTHY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 874.
22. N. SATHYAMURTHY, M. BAER and T. JOSEPH, *Chem. Phys.*, 1987, **114**, 73.
23. J. D. KRESS, R. B. WALKER and E. F. HAYES, *J. Chem. Phys.*, in the press.
24. J. Z. H. ZHANG, D. L. YEAGER and W. H. MILLER, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1990, **173**, 489.
25. V. BALASUBRAMANIAN, B. K. MISHRA, A. BABEL, S. KUMAR and N. SATHYAMURTHY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, in press.